

Kinetics of Oxidation of Phenacyl Bromides by Cerium(IV) Sulphate in Acetic Acid and Sulphuric Acid Media

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The kinetics of oxidation of phenacyl bromides by cerium(IV) sulphate in acetic acid and sulphuric acid media, obeys first order with respect to phenacyl bromides and also with free $[Ce^{4+}]$. The reaction was acid catalysed and the participation of water molecule in the rate determining step has been suggested. The reaction is accelerated by electron withdrawing substituents. The order of reactivity was :

The Hammett's reaction constant is ($\rho = 0.5$). A mechanism involving free radicals and trimerisation of Ce^{4+} has been suggested for the oxidation of phenacyl bromides.

KINETICS of oxidation of several organic compounds by cerium(IV) has been studied by Richardson¹. The literature on the oxidation of halo-organic compounds is meagre and recently we have reported the oxidation of phenacyl bromides by vanadium(V) in sulphuric and perchloric acids². These oxidations exhibit first order dependence on substrate as well as on oxidant and follow free radical pathway and absence of water molecule participation in the reaction steps was confirmed through Hammett's acidity and Bunnett's plots. In this paper we are presenting the kinetics of oxidation of several phenacyl bromides (H, *p*-Br, *m*-Br, *p*-NO₂ and *m*-NO₂) by cerium(IV) sulphate containing acetic and sulphuric acids.

Materials and Methods :

The phenacyl bromide, *m*-bromo-phenacyl bromide and *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide were of Fluka, and *p*-bromophenacyl bromide of Koch—Light and *m*-nitrophenacyl bromide was prepared by the procedure given by Brooks³. The acetic acid used was AnalaR BDH twice refluxed and distilled with chromium trioxide. The sulphuric acid was of BDH, AnalaR and all other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The solutions of phenacyl bromides were prepared by dissolving the required amount in 100% acetic acid and stock solution of cerium(IV) sulphate was prepared by dissolving ceric sulphate in 5*M* sulphuric acid and standardised by standard Fe(II) solution. The methods employed to follow the reaction were same as described earlier².

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

The reaction mixtures containing ten times excess of cerium(IV) with respect to each phenacyl bromide was left at 45°, until there was no change in cerium(IV) concentration. It was observed that

three moles of cerium(IV) were used per one mole of each phenacyl bromide. Hence the stoichiometric equation can be therefore written as :

Corresponding benzoic acids obtained from the oxidation products of phenacyl bromides were characterised, by keeping the reaction mixture with little excess of stoichiometric concentration of cerium(IV) with respect to phenacyl bromide in 3*M* H₂SO₄ and 60% (v/v) acetic acid at 45°, till the reaction was complete. The reaction mixture was then extracted with ether. After removing the acetic acid and ether, the solid product so obtained was treated with sodium bicarbonate and filtered. Acidification of the filtrate gave a solid product which after recrystallisation with hot water gave the melting point of corresponding benzoic acid with $\pm 2^\circ$ variation. Formaldehyde was detected by the chromotropic acid test.

Results

The oxidation reactions for various phenacyl bromides in sulphuric acid medium containing 50-60% (v/v) acetic acid showed first order dependence on [substrate] as well as $[Ce^{4+}]$. The value $k_1/[substrate]$ remains almost constant, and plot of k_1 versus [substrate] passes through origin indicating that the order with substrate is one. Although the first order plots are linear for all the concentrations of cerium(IV), the rate constant k_1 is not independent of initial [Cerium(IV)]. The rate constant k_1 decreases remarkably with increase of [Cerium(IV)] (results are in Table 1).

Table 2 shows the increase of pseudo-first order rate constants with increase in the concentration of

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [SUBSTRATE] AND [Ce(IV)] AT 45°C AND 60% (v/v) ACETIC ACID

[Substrate] [Ce(IV)]		10 ⁴ k ₁ sec ⁻¹ for different substrates				
M	M	Phenacyl bromide	p-bromo phenacyl bromide	m-bromo phenacyl bromide	p-nitro phenacyl bromide	m-nitro phenacyl bromide
0.008	0.004	—	1.20	1.56	3.07	2.10
0.010	0.004	1.35	1.62	1.92	4.20	2.50
0.015	0.004	1.77	2.44	2.86	5.85	3.60
0.020	0.004	2.50	3.42	4.03	7.50	4.72
0.030	0.004	3.60	—	5.76	11.51	—
0.020	0.002	—	4.56	5.83	11.80	7.10
0.020	0.006	2.00	2.66	2.80	5.76	3.90
0.020	0.008	1.60	2.09	2.15	4.22	2.50

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE CONSTANT ON [H₂SO₄] CONCENTRATION

[Substrate] = 1.5 × 10⁻³ M; [Ce(IV)] = 4.0 × 10⁻³ M; Acetic acid = 50% (v/v); temperature = 45°C.

10 ⁴ k ₁ sec ⁻¹ at different sulphuric acid, M							
2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5	5.0	**
Phenacyl bromide							
0.98	1.10	1.27	1.66	2.07	2.70	3.45	0.45
p-bromo phenacyl bromide							
1.08	1.24	1.66	2.20	2.84	3.64	4.80	0.50
m-bromo phenacyl bromide							
1.19	1.38	1.77	2.40	3.11	4.00	5.37	0.52
m-nitro phenacyl bromide							
1.54	2.17	3.06	4.20	5.80	7.60	9.98	0.56
p-nitro phenacyl bromide							
2.85	3.82	4.49	6.05	8.14	10.10	14.60	0.56

** Slopes of Zucker-Hammett plots, i.e., log k₁ versus -H₀.

sulphuric acid. The Zucker-Hammett's⁴ plots log k₁ against -H₀ were linear with slopes of less than unity and the Bunnett's plot⁵ i.e., -(log k₁ + H₀) against -log a_{H₂O} were not linear but gives a positive nature of the curve. The plot of log k₁ against log [H⁺] is not linear. The values of -H₀ and -log a_{H₂O} at various acidities were taken from Paul and Long⁶ and Bunnett⁷, assuming that the values do not change upto 50% acetic acid^{8,9}. The effect of solvent acetic acid¹ on rate was studied from 40 to 80% (v/v) (Table 3). The increase in

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE CONSTANT ON [ACETIC ACID]

[Substrate] = 0.01 M; [Ce(IV)] = 4 × 10⁻³ M; [H₂SO₄] = 3 M; temp. = 45°C

System	10 ⁴ k ₁ sec ⁻¹ at different CH ₃ COOH% (v/v)				
	40	50	60	70	80
Phenacyl bromide	0.76	0.84	1.35	2.20	3.20
p-Bromo phenacyl bromide	1.12	1.24	1.62	2.10	2.80
m-Bromo phenacyl bromide	1.23	1.34	1.92	3.34	—
p-Nitro phenacyl bromide	3.40	3.30	4.20	7.10	—
m-Nitro phenacyl bromide	1.80	1.84	2.53	4.90	—

rate with increase in acetic acid composition upto 50% (v/v) is negligible but above 50% composition the rate increases considerably.

Discussion

Generally α-halo ketones undergo base hydrolysis. If the phenacyl bromide undergoes hydrolysis, it would give phenacyl alcohol and bromide ion. Hence the possibility of acid hydrolysis of various phenacyl bromides in 1M to 5M sulphuric acid in the presence of 50% (v/v) acetic acid was tested. Even after keeping the reaction mixture for several days, there was no formation of bromide ions, indicating absence of acid hydrolysis of phenacyl bromides in the reaction conditions.

The decrease of pseudo-first order rate constant k₁ with increase of [Cerium(IV)] is not unusual (Fig. 1). In the oxidations of citric acid¹⁰, fructose¹¹ and methanol and ethanol^{1,2} the reasons for the retardation of rate with increasing concentration of cerium(IV) is most probably due to unreactive dimer or because of the formation of a stable Ce⁴⁺-substrate complex. Mehrotra *et al*^{13,14}

Fig. 1. Plot of [Cerium(IV)]² against 1/k₁. A = phenacyl-bromide; B = p-Bromo-phenacyl bromide; C = m-Bromo-phenacyl bromide; D = p-Nitro-phenacyl bromide; E = m-Nitro-phenacyl bromide.

discussed the probability of dimeric Ce^{4+} in sulphuric acid media, on the basis of well established existence of dimeric Ce^{4+} in perchlorate¹⁵ and nitrate media¹⁶. From the spectrophotometric study Wiberg and Ford¹⁷ concluded that the principal equilibrium that involved is in between monomeric and trimeric Ce^{4+} in the aqueous acetic acid and perchloric acid media, and also showed that the equilibrium between monomeric and dimeric species is negligible. Hence it may be suggested on the basis of above information and supported by experimental facts that the formation of trimeric Ce^{4+} species in sulphuric acid and acetic acid media may be possible. Due to the formation of trimeric Ce^{4+} species in the reaction the active monomeric Ce^{4+} concentration will decrease considerably and thereby decrease the rate. The rate measurements in sulphuric acid confirm that the reaction is acid catalysed (Table 2). The acceleration in rate with increase in acid concentration might be due to the following equilibria¹⁸.

The Zucker-Hammett's plot of $\log k_1$ against $-H_0$ gave straight lines (Fig. 2, A, B, C, D & E)

Fig. 2. Dependence of rate on H_0 (Plots A, B, C, D and E) and aH_2O (Plots a, b, c, d and e).

A and a = Phenacyl bromide;
 B and b = *p*-Bromo phenacyl bromide;
 C and c = *m*-Bromo phenacyl bromide;
 D and d = *m*-Nitro phenacyl bromide;
 E and e = *p*-Nitro phenacyl bromide.

with slopes of 0.45 to 0.55 for the phenacyl bromides, indicating the participation of water molecule in the reaction steps and this is also confirmed by the positive nature of the curve of Bunnett's plots⁵. The rate was not affected upto 50% (v/v) acetic acid. But above 50% (v/v) acetic acid it increases with increasing percentage of acetic acid. This may be due to the increase in the $-H_0$ values of the reaction mixture^{8,9}.

The following reactions 4 to 8 are the possible steps in the mechanism of oxidations of phenacyl bromides by Ce^{4+} sulphate in 3M sulphuric acid containing 50% (v/v) acetic acid. The step 5 is the formation of free radicals, which is considered to be the rate limiting step.

The bromine which appeared in the step-8 does not interfere with the method of following the kinetics.

The possible C-C fission in the reaction steps was supported by the final oxidation products, i.e., corresponding benzoic acid and formaldehyde. The rate expression can be written for the above mechanism as :

$$\text{rate} = k_2 [Ce^{4+}]_{\text{Free}} [X - C_6H_4COCH_2Br]$$

where k_2 is the rate constant. The formation of Ce^{4+} trimer in acetic acid medium was also proposed by Ford and Wiberg¹⁹ in the oxidation of benzaldehyde. Thus, the correlation between the rate law and observed results justified the existence of unreactive trimeric Ce^{4+} species in sulphuric and acetic acid media.

The oxidation of several substituted phenacyl bromides has been studied, and a plot of $\log k_2$ versus the substituent constant, (*H*, *p*-Br, *m*-Br, *m*-NO₂ and *p*-NO₂) was linear with a positive slope. The Hammett's reaction constant has been found to be 0.5. For para-substituents the σ values²⁰ were taken. The positive value indicates that the rate is

accelerated by the electron withdrawing groups. The order of reactivity was found to be :

The low values of rho indicates the probability of free radicals in the reaction²¹. The formation of the free radicals were also detected by the polymerisation of acrylonitrile when added to the reaction mixture.

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